

Developing, linking, and providing access to supplemental genetics dataset vcf files

Plato L. Smith II, Ph.D.
University of Florida (Libraries)

Lauren McIntyre, Ph.D.
University of Florida (Microbiology)

Abstract

This conference proceeding paper is the written version component of the data panel discussion on developing a dataset collection using [Zenodo](#) for a professor in the Department of Molecular Genetics & Microbiology at the University of Florida.

An internal University of Florida George A. Smathers Libraries [Strategic Opportunities Program](#) (SOP) grant award provided support for the creation and development of an initial supplemental datasets digital collection of large, static variant call format (vcf) in zenodo. The “*Documenting a Genomics Variant Files Data Management: Developing Research Data management (RDM) workflows and providing research data access via HPC*” project inspired this paper. The large vcf datasets used for this project ranged from 34 megabytes to 43 gigabytes. The researcher needed to (1) develop a data repository for supplemental datasets vcf files too large for attachment as supplemental data files for journal submissions, (2) provide digital object identifiers (DOIs) for all vcf dataset files, and (3) link the supplemental vcf dataset files to the journal article via the vcf doi. These three outcomes were accomplished during phase 1 (June 2016 – December 2016) of this project and presented at the GL18. Phase 2 (January 2017 – June 2017) of this project includes performing (1) a dataset reproducibility interview, (2) an open archival initiative protocol for metadata harvest ([OAI-PMH](#)) from Zenodo to the University of Florida institutional repository ([IR@UF](#)), and (3) developing a similar use case project for researchers in UF/IFAS Nature Coast Biological Station ([NCBS](#)).

Introduction

Data continuously extended, stored, and consulted is useful to science (*As We May Think*, Bush, 1945). Data is useful to science if data is accessible, discoverable, and reproducible. This project allows researchers to access, discover, share, and cite large variant call format (VCF) datasets from a data repository. This project can be as a use case scenario for articulating, demonstrating, and detailing the data lifecycle.

Data generation, raw data files are often text files of large sizes. These raw data-effectively what comes off the machine have been a focus for many in terms of collection and preservation. While there has been a huge effort expended in this area for gene expression data, there has been much less effort for capturing and storing

DNA based variant data, and mass spectrometry based metabolomics and proteomic data. As our capacity for data generation continues to expand, thoughtful discussion on what to keep, for how long, and where is an ongoing important public dialogue.

The gene expression and data collection as an example, array images (GEO), or sequence fastq files in the National Center for Biotechnology Information Sequence Read Archive (NCBI SRA) are the raw data. The linking of signal intensity, or number of reads to an identifier is the basis then for all subsequent analysis in the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO). “Geo is a public functional genomics data repository supporting MIAME-compliant data submissions” (NCBI Resources, GEO). Updates, deposition of quantified data, and annotation of the features for the snapshot in time are possible. The quantified processed file is the basis for further analysis and is an intermediate file. Public access and long-term storage of primary data in GEO are important to the research community. The full list of features and the result of whatever analysis done by an individual scientist is then a results file. The results file is often relatively small and it can be included with publication. While not consistently encouraged among all scientific journals, the GSA journals do try to capture this final file and include as supplementary material. Individual scientists should think more carefully about how the inclusion of a full supplement helps their own research long term. Complete data capture, access, storage and reuse enable current and future researchers to start/build research. It obviates the necessity of identifying exactly which file in the folder was the full and final result file. Multiple versions, trainee turnover, and manuscript submission contribute to subtle differences among files on the main analysis system. The final supplement is an opportunity to capture the full information about the analytical results of a particular experiment. This is particularly beneficial if there is any break in the work on any one project, where trainees may not directly overlap. There are, of course, more altruistic reasons for including such files with a paper. However, the main beneficiaries of such preservation are often the lab that generated the results and close collaborators of the project.

As well developed, though imperfectly executed, this data preservation, processing, and sharing paradigm is for gene expression data, for other omics data these steps are significantly more challenging. In attempting to solve these challenges, we present one promising option for scientists to consider, partnerships with their institutional libraries. We describe one scenario here and invite the community to dialogue with us about these ideas.

For some population studies such as the 1000 genomes, special repositories are searchable have been created (). There is no consensus or centralized repository for all pieces and variant information. The affordability of sequencing efforts increases other populations sequencing. SRA (Sequence Read Archive) allows deposits of raw data in the form of sequence reads. Theoretically, full genomes can be stored at NCBI. Sequencing information, data quality, and the deposit workflow of genomes in NCBI needs enhancement. One of the most useful pieces of intermediate data is the list of variants, usually in a standard .vcf format. Depending on the population size, the .vcf files can be quite large. They are certainly cumbersome for inclusion in a journal supplement. It is not at all clear that these are good targets for either NCBI or journal supplements- for one compelling reason- the utility of these files is time limited. After the passage of some time, perhaps ten years, our algorithms will be better, we would

likely prefer to reanalyse the raw data. The argument for semi-permanent storage of raw data is compelling, for intermediate files, it is less so. In some cases, the computational time to regenerate files is negligible. In the case of a vcf file, this is less true as creating these files often takes weeks if not months of computational effort, as well as considerable human effort along the way. There is therefore a good reason to keep these files in the short to medium term. How to keep them and then make them accessible for both the initial research group and the larger public has some current possibilities.

Figure 1. Raw data to SRA, results to journal, vcf to zenodo and IR@UF projected workflows

Researcher need for a vcf data repository

“We can generate terabytes of data about the genetics of population from a myriad of species. As a community, we have even made progress in developing unified data formats for reporting on observed genetic variation (vcf files). Yet, there is no national repository for this information. The libraries represent a transparent, public venue for sharing information on variants.

As a test project, the UFL library has collaborated with investigator Lauren McIntyre on a project in *Drosophila* (fruit fly). A population study of *D. simulans* funded by the NIH where ~200 different *simulans* genotypes were sequenced with 10x-20x coverage were analysed for variants. The resulting variant files have been deposited in the UFL library and links are included in the manuscripts currently under review.” - UF Molecular Genetics & Microbiology Scientist

Using Zenodo as a vcf data repository

Zenodo is a public general research data repository that supports multiple forms of data from publication, poster, presentation, dataset, to image, video/audio, software, and lesson deposits up to 50 Gigabytes per record. The “[Large ‘static’ processed data files](#)” collection in zenodo enables the aggregation, representation, dissemination, and preservation of large, vcf datasets that exceeded the file size limits for supplemental data files for publications. These vcf datasets have digital object identifiers (DOI); and BibTex, CSL, DataCite, Dublin Core, JSON, MARCXML and Mendeley export features. The vcf datasets collection are harvestable via Open Archive Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting ([OAI-PMH](#)) using the Zenodo Harvesting [API for vcf datasets collection](#). The datasets in zenodo are guaranteed access and preservation for at least 20 years. Zenodo support provided an excellent response to request for information on the access, storage, and preservation of the vcf datasets stored in zenodo. The following preservation information about datasets stored in zenodo is useful to the GL18 and [DataONE Users Group](#) communities.

‘Zenodo stores its data as part of CERN's disk-storage service EOS (see <http://information-technology.web.cern.ch/services/eos-service>). This same service is being used for High Energy Physics data storage that is being obtained from CERN's LHC. The data is stored in CERN Data Centre (see general overview of CERN's Data Center here: <http://information-technology.web.cern.ch/about/computer-centre> as well as and more detailed report here on bit-preservation practices: https://cds.cern.ch/record/2195937/files/iPRES2016-CERN_July3.pdf). Additionally on the legal note of data hosting: CERN premises (including the Data Centre) are located on an intergovernmental territory, which is exempt from the host country's local jurisdiction (the host countries for the data centre is Switzerland and France, but as said their legislation does not apply since CERN has a status similar to United Nations).

As for Zenodo's internal workflow for data preservation - we are partially implementing the OAIS model for data archiving (ISO 14721), and are working towards being fully compliant with the model later this year or early next year. In parallel to that we will be working in the near future on fulfilling the requirements to be compliant with the Data Seal of Approval. All records in Zenodo (in all Zenodo collections) are treated equally and are undergoing the same procedures and workflows.

We compute MD5 checksums for all data that is uploaded - this information is visible to the user after upload, as well as returned in the response from the REST API for verification by the user. The checksum comes from the aforementioned CERN's EOS service, which is also used by EOS (alongside other measures) to prevent "bit-rot". For the time being we only generate and extract metadata from software repositories published through our GitHub integration. The metadata is normalized in a sense that its structure and data types are conforming to a pre-defined JSON schema, which is consistent across all records.’ – Zenodo Technical Support, 2016

The screenshot shows the Zenodo website interface. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation links for 'Upload' and 'Communities'. Below the header, the main heading is 'Large 'static' processed data files'. Underneath, there is a section for 'Recent uploads' with a search bar and a list of three dataset entries. Each entry includes the upload date, dataset status, open access status, title, author, abstract, and upload date. To the right, there is a 'Community' section with a word cloud image and a description of the community's purpose, curator information, and a curation policy.

Figure 2. Large ‘static’ processed data files (vcf) repository for access, linking, and sharing

Benefits, features, and outcomes from this project

Some benefits and features from this project include but not limited to the following:

- Genetics project website in Open Science Framework (OSF) – Phase 1
- Genetic vcf datasets collection in [zenodo](#) - (Phase 1)
- DOI for vcf dataset files by DataCite
- Export vcf datasets in multiple formats (e.g. BibTeX, CSL (Citation Style Language) JSON Export, DataCite, Dublin Core, MARCXML, Mendeley)
- vcf datasets data collection harvestable via [OAI-PMH API](#)
- MD5 checksum performed on all uploaded data
- Zenodo partially implementing the OAIS model for data archiving ([ISO 14721:2012](#)) – Space data and information transfer systems - OAIS Reference Model – full compliance later this year or early next year
- Zenodo working in near future on fulfilling the requirements to be compliant with the Data Seal of Approval ([DSA](#))
- Data access/preservation guaranteed for at least 20 years - [FAQ](#)
- Zenodo is US Department of Transportation (DOT) Public Access Plan conformant <http://ntl.bts.gov/publicaccess/repositories.html>

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